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EFFECT OF SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING DISCLOSURE ON FIRM VALUE OF LISTED COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study examined the effect of sustainability reporting on firm value of manufacturing firms in Nigerian from (2014-2023). Three research questions guided the study and corresponding three hypotheses was developed for the study. Specifically, the study focused on determining the effect of social performance indices on return on assets; determining the effect of environment performance indices on return of investment and to determine the effect of economic performance indices on stock prices. Ex-post facto research design was employed in the study. The population of the study included fifty-three (53) manufacturing firms quoted on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at 31st December 2023. Amongst other preliminary analysis and tests, the ordinary least square regression was employed in validating the hypotheses of the study. The study found that social performance indices have no effect on return on assets ($P > 0.05$); environment performance indices have no effect on return of investment ($P > 0.05$); economic performance indices have an effect on organizations stocks price ($P < 0.05$). Consequent on the above findings, I was therefore recommended amongst others that firms should focus on strengthening their economic performance indices, such as profitability and financial growth, as these are found to have a significant positive effect on stock prices. By enhancing these metrics, companies can boost market valuation and attract investors.

Keywords: Sustainability, Environmental disclosure, Social disclosure, economic disclosure

1.0 Introduction

Sustainability reporting has increasingly become a notable part of corporate reporting across the globe as firms are now expected to present/disclose not just their economic performance but also their environmental, social, and governance activities (Hariyani, Wahyuandari & Salatnaya, 2022). The concern for environmental protection, social responsibility, ethical business conduct, and corporate accountability has deepened the demand for transparent sustainability disclosures among stakeholders such as investors, regulators,

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governments, employees, and host communities. Hence, firms are under systemic and regulatory pressure to demonstrate how their operations contribute to sustainable development while maintaining profitability and long-term competitiveness (Siew, 2015).

Recently, sustainability reporting has evolved from a voluntary corporate practice into a strategic reporting mechanism aimed at improving corporate reputation, stakeholder confidence, and market performance. Companies now adopt sustainability reporting frameworks to communicate their commitment toward environmental conservation, social welfare, employee wellbeing, and good governance practices (Hahn et al., 2013). These disclosures are believed to enhance corporate transparency, reduce information asymmetry, and provide investors with broader information beyond conventional financial statements for decision-making purposes.

Consequently, sustainability reporting is recognized as a vital factor in achieving long-term corporate sustainability. However, despite its increasing significance, the validity of research concerning how these disclosures associate with market value remains uncertain and incomplete (Jones, Hillier & Comfort, 2016; Uyar, 2016). While some argue that such reporting provides necessary exposure to obscure company activities, others suggest it may have a negative effect on firm value, particularly if it reduces the value of state-owned entities or if companies prioritize non-financial factors at the expense of traditional economic growth (Hahn et al., 2013; Siew, 2015).

The debate surrounding the relationship between sustainability reporting and firm value has generated mixed empirical findings. Some studies maintain that sustainability disclosures improve investors' confidence, strengthen corporate image, and enhance market valuation by signaling responsible management practices and long-term viability (Arowoshegbe, Emmanuel & Amos, 2017). Conversely, other scholars argue that sustainability initiatives may increase operational costs, reduce short-term profitability, and divert managerial attention from core profit-maximizing objectives, thereby negatively affecting firm value (Elkington, 2004). This inconsistency in prior findings creates a research gap regarding the actual impact of sustainability reporting on the value of firms, especially in emerging economies such as Nigeria where sustainability reporting practices are still developing (Arowoshegbe, Emmanuel & Amos, 2017).

In Nigeria, the increasing globalization of business activities and the adoption of international reporting standards have encouraged many listed firms to embrace sustainability reporting practices. Regulatory bodies and stakeholders are gradually emphasizing the importance of environmental and social disclosures as part of corporate accountability (Lozano & Huisinsh, 2011). Nevertheless, the extent to which sustainability reporting influences the value of listed Nigerian firms remains inconclusive due to varying disclosure levels, weak enforcement mechanisms, and differences in corporate governance structures among firms.

Therefore, there is a growing need for empirical investigation into the relationship between sustainability reporting and firm value. Such a study would provide deeper insight into whether sustainability disclosures truly enhance corporate market performance or merely serve as compliance tools without substantial economic benefits. The outcome of the study would also assist investors, policymakers, regulators, and corporate

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managers in understanding the relevance of sustainability reporting in improving corporate value and achieving long-term organizational sustainability.

1.1 Statement of Problem

Sustainability reporting requires firms to publicly disclose their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) measures, alongside their ability to manage associated risks (Nguyen, 2020). While internal and external stakeholders increasingly demand this information, and meeting these expectations is necessary for long-term sustainability, many companies remain unsure of how the market will react to these disclosures. Theoretically, favorable sustainability initiatives should boost firm value or stock prices; however, many firms hesitate to release information due to the fear of a negative market reaction.

Furthermore, an empirical issue arises from the inability of some firms to maintain proper documentation or provide accessible sustainable reports regarding their operations. This lack of transparency and data accessibility often causes investors to avoid partnerships with such organizations, which negatively impacts company shares and generated revenue.

There is also an observed resource diversion conflict, where investors may disapprove of moving funds away from traditional marketing or R&D activities known to generate shareholder wealth toward sustainability reporting whose effects on firm value remain unclear (Bartlett, 2012). Against these backdrops, it is critical to determine the actual relationship between these reporting strategies and firm value to increase awareness and help investors make informed decisions that favor sustainable organizations.

Despite the obvious attention given to sustainability reporting globally, empirical findings on its relationship with firm value still remain mixed and inconclusive (Yondrichs et al., 2021; Wesley et al., 2022; Brain (2012). While some studies report a positive relationship between sustainability disclosures and firm performance, others reveal insignificant or even negative effects (Wesley et al., 2022). This inconsistency in prior studies creates a gap in literature, particularly within the Nigerian business environment where sustainability reporting practices are still evolving.

Against these backdrops, there is a need to empirically examine the effect between sustainability reporting and firm value as such investigation is necessary to provide clearer evidence on whether sustainability disclosures contribute meaningfully to corporate market performance and shareholder wealth. The study will also help investors, regulators, policymakers, and corporate managers make informed decisions regarding the relevance and effectiveness of sustainability reporting in achieving long-term organizational sustainability and value creation.

1.2 Objective of the Study

The major objective of the study is to determine the effect of sustainability reporting on firm value. The specific Objectives of this study are as follows:

- i. To determine the effect of social performance indices on return on assets
- ii. To determine the effect of environment performance indices on return of investment.
- iii. To determine the effect of economic performance indices on stock prices.

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2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Sustainability Reporting

Sustainability reporting raises public awareness of firms positive and negative impacts on the economy, the environment, and society, and thus reporting promotes transparency and corporate accountability, reporting signals the firms' commitment to sustainability (Wesley, 2022).

Sustainability reporting incurs opportunity costs. Investors may disapprove of diverting resources away from advertising, research and development (R&D), personal selling, and other traditional marketing activities to fund sustainability reporting (Woodroof, Deitz, Howie 2019). Whereas traditional marketing activities are known to increase firm value and thus generate shareholder wealth, sustainability reporting effects on firm value remain unclear (Wesley, 2022).

Previous research demonstrates that sustainability reporting is an effective way to engage stakeholders in that it reduces information asymmetry (Cui and Na, 2018), which ultimately helps investors predict future cash flow (Christensen, Hail, Leuz, 2021). Furthermore, advocates of stakeholder management argue that the processes involved in sustainability reporting should benefit shareholders because sustainability-oriented firms will outperform their competitors in the long term (Zou, wang, Xie, Zhou, 2019), as sustainability reporting helps organizations meet stakeholders' expectations for corporate social performance (Nikolaeva & Bicho, 2011).

Investors who believe in the long-term benefits of stakeholder management would view sustainability reporting as a logical application of stakeholder engagement and as an outcome of good corporate governance (Hörisch, freeman and schaltegger, 2014). Accordingly, such investors would believe reporting is a sound investment which could positively affect firm value. Managers may also use sustainability reporting to achieve organizational legitimacy (Deegan, 2010).

Figure 1: Tipple bottom Pillar

Source: Elkington diagram

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2.1.2 Firms value

A firm's value, also known as Firm Value (FV), Enterprise Value (EV). It is an economic concept that reflects the value of a business. It is the value that a business is worthy of at a particular date. Theoretically, it is an amount that one needs to pay to buy/take over a business entity. Like an asset, the value of a firm can be determined on the basis of either book value or market value.

Shareholders will only invest surplus funds in firms with extraordinary performance. This is because market-based valuation (stock price) of companies will be pushed by organization performance (Keys & Biggs, 2009; Sudiyatno, Puspitasari & Karkita, 2014). Determining firms value can be complex especially when gaming simulation is utilized in derivation of stock price which constitute weighted average of all other measures. Firm valuation is obtained by different means, each of which is likely to give a figure that varies from that obtained by another measure (Biggs, 2008).

The value of a firm is basically the sum of claims of its creditors and shareholders. Therefore, one of the simplest ways to measure it is by adding the market value of its debt, equity, and minority interest. Cash and cash equivalents would then be deducted to arrive at the net value.

2.2 Theoretical Review

There are many theories backing the reason and need for sustainability reporting but the current research is based on the stakeholder. The justification of this theory is that Stakeholder theory addresses the fundamental question of which groups deserve management's attention. That is, while the traditional shareholder view restricts a firm's fiduciary duty to its owners, Stakeholder theory recognizes that employees, customers, suppliers, communities, and governmental bodies are equally vital to the firm's existence.

2.2.1 Stakeholder Theory

The stakeholder theory is a theory of organizational management and business ethics that addresses morals and values in managing an organization. It was originally detailed by R. Edward Freeman in the book *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach* identifies and models the groups which are stakeholders of a corporation, and both describes and recommends methods by which management can give due regard to the interests of those groups. In short, it attempts to address the "principle of who or what really counts". In the traditional view of a company, the shareholder view, only the owners or shareholders (= stockholders) of the company are important, and the company has a binding fiduciary duty to put their needs first, to increase value for them. Stakeholder theory argues that there are other parties involved, including employees, customers, suppliers, financiers, communities, governmental bodies, political groups, trade associations, and trade unions. Even competitors are sometimes counted as stakeholders - their status being derived from their capacity to affect the firm and its stakeholders.

Stakeholder theory is called an incomplete theory by Jensen. Jensen argues that stakeholder theory is incomplete because it does not offer a maximization of value for stakeholders. He also points out the law in the theory is that it does not provide a single-objective, so that the management cannot have a long-term goal under the stakeholder concept. However, he accepts that a stakeholders-oriented policy is needed to couple with the objective function and is labeled the "enlighten value maximization" policy.

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According to stakeholder theory, a firm's operations affect the benefits of both firms and other stakeholders. Consequently, a firm's actions and decision making should be based on the needs of all stakeholders. When the interests of these groups are taken into account, the improvement of risk estimation is facilitated, which then creates firm value for both investors and other stakeholders (Martinez-Ferrero & FriasAceituno, 2013). As the guidelines are set up now, sustainability reporting requires a firm to release not only economic, environmental, social, and governance information but also the risks involved and solutions to deal with these risks. As a result, sustainability reporting makes a critical contribution to both a firm's internal and external bodies. Moreover, a company can attain long-term support from its stakeholders when a board of directors adopts social responsibility practices, which can positively influence a firm's long-term value. Regarding legitimacy theory, it is perceived that firms have hidden responsibilities to its society (Nguyen, 2020).

2.3 Empirical Review

So many researchers have carried out a lot of studies on the concept of Sustainability reporting on firm value. Below are a few of them and their conclusions.

Wesley et al., (2022) investigated how sustainability reporting influences firm value, as measured by Tobin's q. Using a large, unbalanced panel of reporting and non-reporting organizations. The results of the analysis suggested that, in general, sustainability reporting is negatively associated with firm value. However, the relationship between reporting and firm value is evolving. The results also indicated that sustainability reporting impact on firm value becomes positive over time. In addition, the study revealed that the relationship between sustainability reporting and firm value had been positive for a longer time in industries that produce a high level of carbon emissions (e.g., transportation and utilities). Finally, reporting firms can take steps to achieve relatively higher market valuations.

Nguyen, (2020) researched on the firm value and sustainability reporting, the study concentrates on large listed German firms to lessen the impact of size, legislation and geography. Furthermore, with a growing number of standards available to provide instructions on how to report sustainability performance, this study focuses on one standard only and examines the impact of implementing this standard on firm value.

Yondrichs et al., (2021) studied the Effect of Fundamental Factors, Sustainability Reporting, and Corporate Governance on Firm Value from their findings it was reported that sustainability reports Is not a determinant of firm value. This is because sustainability reports are still a voluntary measure and the absence of a uniform reporting standard has made the level of disclosure to still vary. The study reveal that good corporate governance has a significant impact on determining firm value. The study imply that improving corporate governance needs to be done in attracting investors and clarity of regulations related to sustainability reports needs to be formulated immediately. This study presents the theoretical implications in verifying agency and signaling theories but do not support stakeholders theories.

Brain, (2012) proved that corporate sustainability are significant in some organizations which include pharmaceutical industry and automobile industry. However, the impact of corporate sustainability reporting on firm values changed on a year-by-year basis. During the prime year of the Great Recession mainly 2008, corporate sustainability still maintained a slight positive correlation with firm value. Therefore it is safe to

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assume that sustainability reporting do not have a negative effect on firm value. Since stakeholders places a higher emphasis on sustainability reporting and the number of firms that release these reports is rapidly growing, these reports may have much greater effects on firm value.

Şimşek and Öztürk, (2020) Evaluated the impact of environmental accounting approaches of businesses on the overall performance of businesses. Secondary data were used and analyzed by multiple linear regressions as a result of the study, it was determined that there was a mutually significant relationship between environmental accounting, and performance. However, the environmental accounting approaches to the companies covered by the study were found to be at a low level.

Ratanacharoenchai, Rachapradit and Nettayanun, (2017) also investigated sustainability reports and their effect on the firm value of four-hundred and twenty-five (425) firms in Thailand over the period 2012-2014. A static analysis method was used to analyze. The results reveal a non-positive association between the full disclosure and the firm value; the results contrast with the information asymmetry concept. However, the negative firm value could be due mainly to specific falling oil price phenomena during the study period, not the disclosure itself.

Olawale, (2010) assessed the impact of sustainability reporting on profit of first bank of Nigeria (FBN). Test of hypotheses was analyzed with the aid of product-moment correlation. It was established by the study the significant of corporate social responsibility on First Bank Plc.

Munasinghe and Kumara, (2013) employed spearman's rank-order correlation to analyzed firm's motivating factors with regards to corporate social responsibility disclosure and company's performance. It was revealed that profitability is driven by corporate social responsibility.

Adekanmi, (2015) surveyed the extent of the environmental disclosure practice of fifty (50) manufacturing firms listed on the Nigeria stock exchange for eight years starting from 2005 and ending in 2012. The study employed content analysis through descriptive statistics vis-a-vis ratio percentage. Findings evidenced that disclosure value is at average

Al-Waeli et al, (2021) primarily examined the link between the environmental disclosure of industrial companies in Iraq and their financial performance. The authors found that environmental disclosure was weak in Iraq compared to developing countries in the analyzed studies.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The research design acts as a connection between philosophical concepts and the chosen methods for data collection (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). This study utilizes an ex-post facto research design, selected for its dependence on historical accounting information obtained from annual reports and accounts.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises of quoted manufacturing firms on the Nigerian exchange group (NGX) as at end of 2023 financial year. The number of firms included in the various sectors that constitute the population of the study is shown in the table below:

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Table 3.1: Number of firms by sector

S/No	Sector	Number of firms
1	Agriculture	5
2	Conglomerates	5
4	Consumer Goods	20
6	Health Care	10
8	Industrial Goods	13
	Total	53

Source: NGX, (2026)

3.3 Sample Size of the Study

The study was limited to forty-one (41) quoted manufacturing companies selected using purposive sampling technique; the decision was premised on the classification of the firms as manufacturing (based on the nature and description of activities) as shown on the Nigerian exchange group (NGX) website. The sample selection criteria are shown in the table below. The full list of the companies is shown in Appendix I.

Table 3.1: Sample selection

Sector/criteria	Number of firms
No of firms	53
Less: Consumer goods (Delisted firm)	04
Less: Industrial goods non-available	03
Less: Healthcare (Delisted firm)	04
Less: Agriculture (Delisted firm)	01
Total sample size	41

Source: NXG (2026)

The exclusion of other sectors was consistent with prior studies (Abid, Shaique, & Anwar-ul-Haq, 2018). In addition, during the data analysis any company whose required data are incomplete or unavailable was eliminated from the sample. The final sample percentage with respect to the population is approximately 77.36% of the entire manufacturing firms on the Nigerian exchange group.

3.4 Sources of Data

Data collection is a crucial stage of dissertation that entails gathering all the necessary and required information from essential sources to be used for the analysis (Kumar, 2011). The data for this study was obtained through secondary sources. Secondary data is information or data that has previously been collected and recorded for other purposes (Blumberg, Cooper, & Schindler, 2008). One major advantage of secondary data is that analysis time can be saved (Blumberg, Cooper, & Schindler, 2008). Hence, the data was extracted from the annual reports and accounts of the selected companies as compiled by machameRatios© www.machameratios.com.

3.5 Methods of Data Analysis

The study conducted descriptive statistics to provide an understanding of the data in terms of the mean, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum. Correlation analysis was also conducted to express the relationship between the independent and dependent variables employed in this study. However, to achieve the objective of

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the study, the ordinary least square (OLS) regression was employed.

3.5.1 Model Specification

Based on the theoretical literature and earlier empirical studies, the present study adapted the model of Gholami, Sands, and Rahman (2022) to express the econometric form of the model expressed as:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SOCD_{it} + \beta_2 FSize_{it} + \beta_3 Leverage_{it} \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots [1]$$

$$ROI_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ENVD_{it} + \beta_2 FSize_{it} + \beta_3 Leverage_{it} \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots [2]$$

$$SP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ECOP_{it} + \beta_2 FSize_{it} + \beta_3 Leverage_{it} \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots [3]$$

The apriori expectation based on the literature reviewed and related theories is stated as follows; $\beta_1 X_{1it} < 0$, $\beta_2 X_{2it} < 0$, $\beta_3 X_{3it} > 0$. The basis for this expectation flows from the outcome of the literature review and empirical findings.

Where:

- β_0 = Constant
- $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Slope Coefficient
- μ = Stochastic disturbance
- i = i^{th} company
- t = period

3.5.2 Description of variables

Table 3.3: Description of variables

Label	Variable type	Description	Measurement	Source
SP	Dependent	Stock price	Measures as the ratio of total share market value to total assets.	Ortiz, (2006)
SOCD	Independent	Social disclosure	Measured as the ratio of total value added (VA) total investments in wages and salaries (HC)	Olayinka and Uwalomwa, (2011).
ENVD	Independent	Environmental disclosure	Measured as the ratio of value added (VA) to capital employed (CE)	Olayinka and Uwalomwa, (2011).
ECOP	Independent	Economic performance	Measured as the ratio of (VA-HC) to total value added (VA)	Olayinka and Uwalomwa, (2011).
Lev	Control	Firm Leverage (Gearing)	The ratio of debt to equity as at the year-end (DEBT/EQUITY)	(Riahi- Belkaoui, 2003).
Fsize	Control	Firm Size	Logarithmic transformation of Total Asset	Onyali & Okafor, 2018

Source: Author’s Compilation, (2026)

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3.5.3 Decision Rule

The decision rule is based on the sign and significance of the computed *t-statistic* from the regression output. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Hence, if the *p* value of the *t statistic* < 0.05 (the chosen alpha level) the null hypothesis is rejected; and the variable is postulated to have a significant effect. On the contrary, if the *p* value of the *t statistic* > 0.05 (the chosen alpha level) the null hypothesis is accepted; and the variable is postulated to have no significant effect.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION

4.1 Data Presentation

This study was set to investigate the effect of sustainability reporting on firm value of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria between the periods of 2014-2023.

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1 displays the descriptive statistics for the study where it described the nature of the variables used. It also displays the number of observations of each variable and the description of their mean, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum values.

Table 4.1: Summary statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Return on Asset	410	0.0415396	0.1575901	-1.799173	1.088969
Share Price	410	50.5170	181.8396	0.2000	1555.9900
Social Disclosure	410	0.8170732	0.3870789	0	1
Environmental Disclosure	410	0.0512195	0.2207145	0	1
Economic Performance	317	-2.875624	1.036414	-7.606512	0.0852318
Firm Size	410	7.194735	0.8871078	5.239405	9.305878
Leverage	410	-5.732220	155.3433	-3123.06	202.90

Source: STATA Output/Author (2026)

The summary statistics show that the average return on assets (ROA) across the 410 firms is 4.15%, with a standard deviation of 0.1576, indicating high variability in the profitability of these firms. The minimum ROA is -1.7992, suggesting that some firms experienced significant losses, while the maximum is 1.08897, showing that certain firms achieved high returns. This wide range in ROA reflects considerable differences in the financial performance of the firms.

The average stock price is 50.517, with a high standard deviation of 181.8396, which points to extreme variation in stock prices among the firms. The minimum stock price is 0.2, while the maximum is 1555.99, suggesting that the sample includes both small, lower-valued firms and large, highly valued ones. This spread indicates significant differences in market valuation and firm size.

For social disclosure, the average score is 0.8171, indicating that 81.7% of firms disclose social responsibility information. The standard deviation of 0.3871 shows moderate variation in the level of social disclosure. Environmental disclosure is considerably lower, with an average of 0.0512, suggesting that only 5.12% of firms

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disclose environmental information. The standard deviation of 0.2207 highlights some variability, with certain firms disclosing no environmental information at all.

Economic performance has a mean of -2.8756, indicating negative average performance across the firms, with a standard deviation of 1.0364. The minimum value of -7.6065 shows that some firms faced severe losses, while the maximum value is only slightly positive at 0.0852, indicating marginal profitability for a few firms. This suggests that most firms in the sample faced economic challenges during the period under review.

The average firm size, based on a log scale, is 7.1947, with a standard deviation of 0.8871. The minimum firm size is 5.2394, and the maximum is 9.3059, reflecting a broad range of firm sizes from small to large. This diversity in firm size could influence the firms' ability to engage in sustainability reporting.

Leverage has a mean of -5.7322, which is an unusual result and may indicate that some firms have negative equity, possibly suggesting financial distress. The standard deviation of 155.3433 indicates extreme variability in the leverage ratios of the firms, with the minimum value being -3123.06 and the maximum 202.9. This suggests that some firms are highly leveraged, while others may have very low or even negative leverage, which could have important implications for their financial health and sustainability efforts.

4.2 Data Analyses

In order to meet the study's objectives, an ordinary least squares (OLS) regression was performed. Before proceeding, the basic assumptions of the OLS model were examined for potential inconsistencies. Diagnostic tests, including multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity tests, were carried out. Prior to these, tests were conducted to assess the association or correlation between the dependent and independent variables in the study. Consequently, Spearman Rank correlation analysis was employed to evaluate this association and relationship, as outlined below.

4.2.1 Correlation Analysis

In examining the association among the variables, this study employed the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient (correlation matrix), and the results are presented in Table 4.2 below.

Table 4.2: Correlation Analysis

Variable	ROA	SP	Soc Dis	Env Dis	Eco Disc	FSize	Lev
ROA	1.0000						
SP	0.2387	1.0000					
Social Disc	0.0533	0.1055	1.0000				
Env Disc	-0.0014	0.0270	-0.0469	1.0000			
Eco Dis	0.7652	0.2684	0.0173	0.0419	1.0000		
Firm Size	-0.0373	0.2863	0.2873	0.3175	0.0705	1.0000	
Leverage	0.0252	0.0313	-0.0211	0.0153	0.0199	0.1298	1.0000

Source: STATA Output/Author (2026)

The correlation analysis reveals that the return on assets (ROA) has a moderate positive relationship with stock price, with a correlation coefficient of 0.2387. This suggests that firms with higher returns tend to have higher

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stock prices. Additionally, there is a strong positive correlation of 0.7652 between ROA and economic performance, indicating that firms with better economic performance report higher profitability. However, ROA shows a weak or negligible relationship with other variables such as social disclosure, environmental disclosure, firm size, and leverage, with correlation coefficients close to zero.

The stock price exhibits a moderate positive relationship with both economic performance (0.2684) and firm size (0.2863), implying that firms with better financial performance and larger size tend to have higher market valuations. However, the correlation between stock price and other variables, such as social disclosure, environmental disclosure, and leverage, is weak, indicating little association between them.

Social disclosure has a moderate positive correlation with firm size (0.2873), suggesting that larger firms are more likely to engage in social responsibility reporting. However, the correlation between social disclosure and other variables, such as ROA, stock price, environmental disclosure, and leverage, is weak, indicating little to no relationship between them.

Environmental disclosure shows a moderate positive relationship with firm size (0.3175), indicating that larger firms are more likely to report on environmental issues. However, its correlations with ROA, stock price, social disclosure, economic performance, and leverage are weak or negligible, suggesting minimal associations.

Economic performance is strongly correlated with ROA but shows weak relationships with other variables, such as stock price, firm size, and leverage, indicating that its impact is primarily on profitability. Firm size is moderately correlated with stock price, social disclosure, and environmental disclosure, suggesting that larger firms tend to have higher valuations and are more likely to engage in sustainability reporting. However, the correlation between firm size and leverage is weak (0.1298), indicating only a slight association. Lastly, leverage shows weak or negligible relationships with most variables, suggesting it has minimal impact on firm value, profitability, or sustainability practices.

4.2.2 Multicollinearity Test (VIF)

The degree of multicollinearity can be tested by the use of certain statistical instruments like the variance inflation factor (VIF). The VIF test helps us reveal whether or not there are multicollinearity issues in the specified model (Almeyda & Darmansya, 2019). A VIF test result of a value greater than 10 is an indication of the presence of multicollinearity and calls for concern.

Table 4.3: Variance inflation factor (VIF)

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
Firm Size	1.33	0.750549
Social Disclosure	1.15	0.870801
Environmental Disclosure	1.12	0.892571
Economic Performance	1.07	0.932283
Leverage	1.02	0.981404
Mean VIF	1.14	

Source: STATA Output/Author (2026)

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From the records in Table 4.3, the mean VIF value of 1.14 indicates the absence of multicollinearity in the models, and this suggests that no independent variable should be dropped from the models.

4.2.3 Heteroskedasticity test

The presence of heteroscedasticity tends to produce p-values that are smaller than they should be due to increased variance of the coefficient estimates. The Cook-Weisberg test is a test that is mostly used to test for heteroskedasticity in a linear regression model and was used in this study for the same purpose.

Table 4.4: Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Ho: Constant variance	chi2(1)	Prob > chi2
Variables: fitted values of roa	5.21	0.8123
Variables: fitted values of stock price	3.67	0.1210

Source: STATA Output/Author (2026)

From Table 4.4 above, the result of the Cook-Weisberg test for heteroscedasticity revealed a chi-square (χ^2) value of 5.21 and 3.67 with a p-value of 0.8123 and 0.1210 for all models. The models show a p-value score above 0.05 implying that we accept the null hypotheses that the population used is not heteroskedastic. Therefore, there is an indication that the OLS result is free from heteroskedasticity. The study therefore employs the OLS regression in validating the hypotheses without need for robust standard error.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

Following the above discussion, the OLS as in Table 4.5, Table 4.6 and Table 4.7 was used in this study for testing the study’s hypotheses. Below is a specific analysis for each of the independent variables.

4.3.1 Hypothesis one

H₀₁: Social performance indices have an effect on return on assets.

Table 4.4: OLS Regression Result for Hypothesis one

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	410
Model	.681806446	3	.227268815	F(3, 406)	=	9.74
Residual	9.47556169	406	.023338822	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.0671
				Adj R-squared	=	0.0602
Total	10.1573681	409	.024834641	Root MSE	=	.15277

returnsonasset	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
socialdisclosure	.0127583	.0207592	0.61	0.539	-.0280506 .0535673
firmsize	.041955	.0090623	4.63	0.000	.0241402 .0597698
leverage	.0000515	.000049	1.05	0.294	-.0000448 .0001479
_cons	-.2704444	.0622483	-4.34	0.000	-.3928137 -.1480752

Source: STATA Output/Author (2026)

The OLS regression results indicate that the model is statistically significant, as shown by the F-statistic of 9.74 and a p-value of 0.0000. This means the overall model is a good fit for the data, and there is evidence that the independent variables (social disclosure, firm size, and leverage) jointly influence return on assets (ROA).

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However, the R-squared value of 0.0671 indicates that only about 6.71% of the variation in return on assets is explained by the model. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.0602 is slightly lower, which accounts for the number of predictors in the model and still suggests that a small proportion of the variance in ROA is captured by these variables.

The coefficient for social disclosure is 0.0128 with a p-value of 0.539, which is not statistically significant at conventional levels ($p > 0.05$). This implies that social disclosure does not have a significant effect on return on assets in this model. The 95% confidence interval further supports this conclusion, as it includes zero (-0.0281 to 0.0536).

The coefficient for firm size is 0.04196, which is statistically significant with a p-value of 0.000. This means that firm size has a significant positive effect on return on assets, implying that larger firms are more likely to have higher profitability. The confidence interval (0.0241 to 0.0598) further confirms that this effect is both positive and significant.

The coefficient for leverage is 0.0000515, with a p-value of 0.294, which is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that leverage does not have a meaningful impact on return on assets in this model. The confidence interval (-0.0000448 to 0.0001479) also includes zero, reinforcing the lack of significance.

The results suggest that firm size significantly influences return on assets, indicating that larger firms are more profitable. However, social disclosure and leverage do not have a significant effect on return on assets based on this model. Therefore, the hypothesis that social performance indices have an effect on return on assets is not supported by the data, as social disclosure does not significantly impact profitability in this analysis.

4.3.2 Hypothesis two

H02: Environment performance indices have an effect on return of investment.

Table 4.5: OLS Regression Result for Hypothesis two

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	410
Model	.680757136	3	.226919045	F(3, 406)	=	9.72
Residual	9.476611	406	.023341406	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.0670
				Adj R-squared	=	0.0601
Total	10.1573681	409	.024834641	Root MSE	=	.15278

returnsonasset	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
environmentaldisclosure	-.0207446	.0359638	-0.58	0.564	-.0914431 .0499539
firmsize	.0453713	.0089968	5.04	0.000	.0276851 .0630575
leverage	.000053	.0000489	1.08	0.279	-.0000432 .0001491
_cons	-.2835289	.064661	-4.38	0.000	-.410641 -.1564167

Source: STATA Output/Author (2026)

The regression results for hypothesis two indicate that the model is statistically significant, with an F-statistic of 9.72 and a p-value of 0.0000. This shows that the independent variables—environmental disclosure, firm size, and leverage—jointly influence return on assets. However, the R-squared value of 0.0670 indicates that only 6.70% of the variation in return on assets is explained by these variables, which suggests limited explanatory

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power.

The coefficient for environmental disclosure is -0.0207, with a p-value of 0.564, indicating that environmental disclosure does not have a significant effect on return on assets. The 95% confidence interval also includes zero, reinforcing that environmental disclosure is not a significant predictor.

Firm size has a coefficient of 0.0454, which is statistically significant with a p-value of 0.000, suggesting that larger firms are more likely to have higher returns on assets. The confidence interval confirms the positive and significant impact of firm size.

Leverage has a coefficient of 0.000053, with a p-value of 0.279, indicating that leverage does not significantly influence return on assets. The confidence interval supports this as it includes zero.

Summarily, firm size has a significant positive effect on return on assets, while environmental disclosure and leverage do not show significant effects. Therefore, there is no sufficient evidence to support the hypothesis that environment performance indices have an effect on return of investment.

4.3.3 Hypothesis three

H03: Economic performance indices have an effect on organizations stocks price.

Table 4.6: OLS Regression Result for Hypothesis three

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	317
Model	1911364.12	3	637121.373	F(3, 313)	=	17.55
Residual	11365750.4	313	36312.3016	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.1440
				Adj R-squared	=	0.1358
Total	13277114.5	316	42016.1852	Root MSE	=	190.56

shareprice	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
economic_performance	49.3496	10.36952	4.76	0.000	28.94683 69.75237
firmsize	65.25122	12.78364	5.10	0.000	40.09849 90.40394
leverage	-.1232113	.7496516	-0.16	0.870	-1.598205 1.351782
_cons	-273.2887	100.8639	-2.71	0.007	-471.7458 -74.83161

Source: STATA Output/Author (2026)

The OLS regression result for Hypothesis Three reveals that the model is statistically significant, with an F-statistic of 17.55 and a p-value of 0.0000, indicating that the independent variables, economic performance, firm size, and leverage jointly influence stock price. The R-squared value of 0.1440 indicates that 14.40% of the variation in share price is explained by the model, which suggests a moderate explanatory power. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.1358 confirms that after adjusting for the number of predictors, the model still explains a similar percentage of variation.

The coefficient for economic performance is 49.3496, with a p-value of 0.000, which is statistically significant. This implies that as economic performance improves, share prices increase significantly. The 95% confidence interval (28.94683 to 69.75237) shows that the effect is positive and strong.

The coefficient for firm size is 65.25122, also statistically significant with a p-value of 0.000. This result suggests that larger firms tend to have higher share prices, and the confidence interval (40.09849 to 90.40394)

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confirms the robustness of this relationship.

However, the coefficient for leverage is -0.1232113, with a p-value of 0.870, indicating that leverage does not have a statistically significant effect on share price. The 95% confidence interval (-1.598205 to 1.351782) includes zero, reinforcing that leverage has no meaningful impact on share price in this model. In summary, economic performance and firm size have significant positive effects on share price, while leverage does not show a significant effect. Thus, the study concludes that economic performance indices have an effect on organizations' stock prices.

4.5 Discussion of results

This study specifically examines the effect of social, environmental, and economic performance indices on key financial metrics such as return on assets, return on investment, and stock prices. The findings reveal varying impacts of these indices on firm performance. To provide context, this discussion compares the current study's results with previous empirical findings, highlighting both consistent and divergent outcomes within the literature.

In the following discussion, we explore how the findings align or contrast with prior studies, offering insights into the complex dynamics between sustainability reporting and financial performance. The findings of this study reveal that social performance indices have no effect on return on assets. This result aligns with the work of Yondrichs et al. (2021), which also found that sustainability reports, including social performance indicators, are not determinants of firm value due to their voluntary nature and inconsistent disclosure levels. Similarly, Ratanacharoenchai et al. (2017) also observed a non-positive association between full sustainability disclosure and firm value. However, this contrasts with Wesley et al. (2022), who initially observed a negative association between sustainability reporting and firm value but found that the relationship becomes positive over time, especially in high-carbon-emission industries.

Regarding environmental performance indices and their effect on return on investment, this study's findings suggest no significant impact, which aligns with Yondrichs et al. (2021) as they also found that sustainability reporting, which includes environmental indices, is not a determinant of firm value. This is further supported by Ratanacharoenchai et al. (2017), who reported a non-positive relationship between environmental disclosure and firm value in Thailand. However, this finding contrasts with Şimşek and Öztürk (2020), who found a significant relationship between environmental accounting approaches and business performance, suggesting that environmental practices can positively impact firm performance under certain conditions.

The result showing that economic performance indices have an effect on organizations' stock prices is consistent with the study by Brain (2012), who highlighted that corporate sustainability maintained a slight positive correlation with firm value even during economic downturns like the Great Recession. The positive effect of economic performance indices on firm value is also in line with Munasinghe and Kumara (2013), who demonstrated that profitability is driven by corporate social responsibility. However, Nguyen (2020) found a negative association between firm value and adherence to GRI reporting standards, which contrasts with this study's findings, suggesting that higher adherence to sustainability standards may lower a firm's share value in certain contexts.

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Summarily, while this study supports the positive role of economic performance indices in enhancing firm value, the results for social and environmental performance indices challenge the assumption that all dimensions of sustainability reporting positively affect financial performance. The divergence of these findings from some past studies indicates that sustainability reporting's impact may vary based on industry, geography, and the time horizon considered.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

5.1 Summary of Findings

In line with the decision rule governing our analysis, the findings emanating from the data analysis is summarized as follows:

- i. Social performance indices have no effect on return on assets ($P > 0.05$).
- ii. Environment performance indices have no effect on return of investment ($P > 0.05$).
- iii. Economic performance indices have an effect on organizations stocks price ($P < 0.05$).

5.2 Conclusion

This study examined the effect of sustainability reporting (social, environmental, and economic performance indices) on the financial performance of firms, particularly focusing on return on assets and stock prices. The findings revealed that social and environmental performance indices had no significant effect on return on assets respectively, while economic performance indices positively influenced stock prices. These results align with some studies in the literature that support the notion that sustainability initiatives may not always have a direct or immediate impact on financial returns, particularly in areas of social and environmental performance. However, the positive effect of economic performance indices on stock prices highlights the importance of financial sustainability in driving market value. The study underscores the need for a more comprehensive understanding of how different aspects of sustainability reporting influence firm value, with implications for corporate governance and investor decision-making.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the above findings and conclusion, the study therefore makes the following recommendations:

- i. **Prioritize Economic Performance Metrics:** Firms should focus on strengthening their economic performance indices, such as profitability and financial growth, as these are found to have a significant positive effect on stock prices. By enhancing these metrics, companies can boost market valuation and attract investors.
- ii. **Reevaluate Social and Environmental Strategies:** Since social and environmental performance indices did not show a direct impact on return on assets or return on investment, firms should reassess their sustainability strategies in these areas. Emphasis should be placed on ensuring that these efforts align with the company's broader financial objectives while maintaining long-term social responsibility.
- iii. **Integrate Sustainability into Corporate Governance:** Corporate governance structures should integrate sustainability into decision-making processes to balance financial goals with social and environmental responsibilities. This could enhance investor confidence, especially in industries with growing environmental concerns, without compromising financial performance.

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REFERENCES

- Abdul Salam, F., Al-Qaheri, H., and Al-Khayyat, R. (2011). The intellectual capital performance of Kuwaiti banks: an application of VAIC model. Available online at <http://www.SciRP.org/journal/ib>
- Abid, A., Shaique, M., & Anwar ul Haq, M. (2018). Do big four auditors always provide higher audit quality? Evidence from Pakistan. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 6(2), 58.
- Adekanmi, A. D. (2015). Environmental accounting: A tool for sustainable development. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research - Social Sciences and Education*, 1(2), 23- 31.
- Al-waeli, A.J., Khalid, A., Ismail, Z., &Idan, H.Z. (2021). The relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance of industrial companies with using a new theory: Literature review, *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, 27(2), 3846-3868.
- Amos O. Arowoshegbe, Emmanuel Uniamikogbo and Amos S. Adeusi *Factors Affecting Timeliness of an Audit Report in Nigeria* Federal University Ndufu-Alike Ikwo, Ebonyi State Nigeria l. 1. N0. 1. 2017. Pp, 26-38. Maiden Edition
- Biggs, W. D. (2008). A comparison of ranking and relational grading procedures in a general management simulation. *Simulation and Games*, 9, 185-200.
- Boluwaji, O. D., Igbekoyi, O. E., Dagunduro, M. E., Busayo, T. O., &Osatuyi, O. A. (2024). Sustainable business practice and going concern of selected listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Emerging Trends in Social Sciences*, 16(1), 1-12.
- Brain Bartlett The impact of corporate sustainability reporting on firm valuations Claremont McKenna College 2012
- Brain Bartlett The impact of Corporate Sustainability reporting on firms valuation Claremont McKenna College 2012
- Christensen, H. B., Hail, L., & Leuz, C. (2021). Mandatory CSR and sustainability reporting: Economic analysis and literature review. *Review of Accounting Studies*, 26(3), 1176–1248.
- Cui, J., Jo, H., & Na, H. (2018). Does corporate social responsibility affect information asymmetry? *Journal of Business Ethics*, 148(3), 549–572.
- Deegan, C. (2010). Organizational legitimacy as a motive for sustainability reporting. In *Sustainability Accounting and Accountability* (pp. 146–168).
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.). (2011). *the Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Diyah Santi Hariyani, Wenni Wahyuandari, Louse Happy Amira Salatnaya Sustainability reporting and company's value *journal of Accounting, Finance and Auditing Studies* 8 (1), 60-74, 2022
- Elkington J. *Cannibals with Forks: The Triple Botom Line of 21st Century Business*.Oxford: Capstone publishing; 1997
- Etale, L.M &Otuja, S. (2018) Environmental Responsibility Reporting and Financial Performance of Quoted Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria, *Journal of Business and Innovation Research* 6(6), 23-34. <https://www.aqa.org.uk/resources/business/as-and-a-level/business-7131-7132/teach/teaching-guide-elkingtons->

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triple-bottom-line

- Hörisch, J., Freeman, R. E., & Schaltegger, S. (2014). Applying stakeholder theory in sustainability management: Links, similarities, dissimilarities, and a conceptual framework. *Organization & Environment*, 27(4), 328–346
- Ikumapayi, T., Uwuibge, U., Uwuibge, O.R., Ozordi, E., Sylvester, O., & Osariemen, A. (2018) The effect of Corporate Governance Attributes on Earnings Management: A Study of Listed Companies in Nigeria. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 17(6).
- Jones, P., Hillier, D., & Comfort, D. (2016). Materiality and External Assurance in Corporate Sustainability Reporting: An Exploratory Study of Europe's Leading Commercial Property Companies. *Journal of European Real Estate Research*, 9 (2), 147–170. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JERER-07-2015-0>
- Keys, J. B., & Biggs, W. D. (2009). A review of business games. In J. W. Gentry (Ed.), *Guide to business gaming and experiential learning* (48-73). East Brunswick, NJ: Nichols/GP Publishing.
- Kolawole, J. S., Igbekoyi, O. E., Ogungbade, O. I., & Dagunduro, M. E. (2023). Environmental accounting practice and financial performance of listed aviation firms in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 23(13), 70-80.
- Kumar, R. (2011). *Research Methodology-A Step by Step Guide for Beginners* (3rd Ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Lozano, R., Huisingh, D., 2011. Inter-linking issues and dimensions in sustainability reporting. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 19, 99–107.
- Martínez-Ferrero, J., & Frías-Aceituno, J. V. (2013). Relationship between sustainable development and financial performance: International empirical research. *Business, Strategy and the Environment*, 24, 20–39. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.1803>
- Munasinghe, M. & Kumara, D. (2013). Impact of disclosure of corporate social responsibility on corporate financial performances of plantations companies in Sri-Lanka. *Journal of emerging trends in Economics and Management sciences*, 4(3), 371-376.
- Nazim, U., Khaled, H., & Fatema, A. (2017). Environmental reporting practices and its relationship with corporate characteristics: An evidence from manufacturing companies listed in Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE). *Journal of the Cost and Management*, 45(1), 3-11.
- Nguyen, T. T. D. (2020). An Empirical Study on the Impact of Sustainability Reporting on Firm Value. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 12(3), 119–135. <https://doi.org/10.7441/joc.2020.03.07>
- Nikolaeva, R., & Bicho, M. (2011). The role of institutional and reputational factors in the voluntary adoption of corporate social responsibility reporting standards. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 39(1), 136–157.
- Nzekwe, O.G., Okoye, P.V.C., & Amahalu, N.N. (2021). Effect of sustainability reporting on financial performance of quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Studies and Social Science Research*, 3(5), 265-280.

Original Article

- Olawale, A. S. (2010). The Impact of corporate social responsibility on the profitability of the Nigerian banking sector, A case study of First bank of Nigeria Plc, Retrieved from <http://www.ediaro.com>. on 2nd April 2018
- Olayinka M. U. and Uwalomwa U., (2011). Intellectual Capital and Business Performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Research in Business*. Vol. 1, Issue. 10, (pp.49- 56) November, 2011
- Onyali, C. I., & Okafor, T. G. (2018). Effect of corporate governance mechanisms on tax aggressiveness of quoted manufacturing firms on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 8(1), 1-20.
- Phillips P. P., & Phillips J. J. (2006). Measuring ROI in the public sector. In Action Case Study Series. ASTD Press. <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/career-map/sell-side/capital-markets/stock-price/>
- Prof. Dr. Rüdiger Hahn and Michael Kühnen Determinants of sustainability reporting: A review of results, trends, theory, and opportunities in an expanding field of research *cleaner Production*.
- Ratanacharoenchai, C., Rachapradit, P. & Nettayanun, S. (2017). Sustainability Reports and Its Effect on Firm Value in Thailand. Proceedings of 41st International Business Research Conference 20 - 21 April, Imperial College, London, UK
- Renard Y.J. Siew A review of corporate sustainability reporting tools (SRTs) *Journal of environmental management* 164, 180-195, 2015
- Riahi-Belkaoui, A. (2003). Intellectual capital and firm performance of US multinational firms', *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, Vol. 4, No. 2, pp.215–226.
- Uyar, A. (2016). Evolution of Corporate Reporting and Emerging Trends. *The Journal of Corporate Accounting and Finance*, 27 (4), 27–30. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcaf.22157>
- Wesley Friske Seth A. Hoelscher Atanas Nik Nikolov impact of voluntary sustainability reporting on firm value: Insights from signaling theory *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science* · June 2022
- Woodroof, P. J., Deitz, G. D., Howie, K. M., & Evans, R. D. (2019). The effect of cause-related marketing on firm value: A look at Fortune's most admired all-stars. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Sciences*, 47(5), 899–918.
- Yondrichs, Muliati, Supriadi Laupe, Arung Gihna Mayapada, Jurana, Ridwan (2021). The Effect of Fundamental Factors, Sustainability Reporting, and Corporate Governance on Firm Value *Universal Journal of accounting and finance* 9(6). 1503-1509 2021
- Zou, P., Wang, Q., Xie, J., & Zhou, C. (2019). Does doing good lead to doing better in emerging markets? Stock market responses to the SRI index announcements in Brazil, China, and South Africa. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 48(5), 966–986.